

The Resort Brand Personality

A Study on Long Term Period Online Reviews 2008 - 2020

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Abstract: The long-term brand personality research is scarce, this research utilizes the availability of online reviews dataset in TripAdvisor to construct the resort brand personality in Bali, Indonesia. This research spans from 2008 through 2020. The online reviews data is cleansed once it is collected, for further exploratory factor analysis based on the Aaker brand personality dictionary. The findings show that sincerity is the dominant dimension from, the second dominant dimension is sophistication, while the third is excitement, this dimension is concerned with cheerfulness as something new, energetic, and bright character of the resort.

Keywords: TripAdvisor, Online Reviews, Long Period, Brand Personality, Resort

I. INTRODUCTION

A long-term brand personality is built on the consumer's perception of the brand's experience and the variety of contact points with the brand. This customer experience was obtained from online reviews on the social media site. In the context of hospitality, the customer of the TripAdvisor is relevant to create the entity's long-term brand personality, based on a long period of online reviews of data set accessible in the platform [1].

A long-term observation is conceivable because they are enabled by the technological platform, which serves as a repository for online customer feedback. All of this experience is published in online reviews, which use English as the global language, and all of the online reviews may be retrieved from anywhere and at any time. Because the data is now available from the platform, it is possible to perform study for longer horizontal years of dataset. The research was carried out over a lengthy period of time, from 2008 to 2020 [2-4].

The online reviews are based on the users' experiences as well as their preferences as expressed on the platform. As a result, it is not a structured data set with the same unit of information for each sample, but rather a diversity of unit of information dependent on each sample. An unstructured data collection, to put it simply, is not a predetermined questionnaire[5]. The online reviews in travel advisors also include numerous units of information, complaints are information about discontent with the goods or services. There is also a positive attitude, indicating pleasure with the entity's services. As a result, the information on TripAdvisor is useful for management in terms of the entity's performance [6].

Despite the fact that the online reviews dataset is rich in information, there is a dearth of study employing the online reviews for sensemaking customer behavior. Because the nature of the information differs from that of the questionnaire, the procedure for utilizing the data differs as well. The strategy, as well as the process of sense creation, will be initiated in order to enhance the field of consumer behavior [7].

Since we are transitioning from a traditional market to a digital environment, from brick and mortar to market space. Furthermore, the Covid 19 epidemic has expedited the deployment of technology at every point of contact with our process-consuming goods and services. As a result, the use of unstructured datasets is critical, particularly in hospitality, which is significantly associated with consumer experience [8-10].

II. REVIEW LITERATURE

Previous study has been performed through observation on Twitter and Facebook, which give a statement and online reviews linked to the goods and services. This is likewise an unstructured text, as are the travel advisor internet reviews [5][11-13]. Because the nature of a dataset is the number of unit data points, the approach to use and sense producing the dataset is classifying the information we have inside the dataset. However, there is an issue since there are a variety of datasets, so manually creating all of the data sets would take a long time, therefore doing the analysis using software is required [14].

A product or service has a personality, and that personality reflects the thing. There are five dimensions in the idea of brand personality, which are SSECR (Sincerity, Sophistication, Excitement, Competence, and Ruggedness), which govern the character portrayed by the goods or services [15][16][17][18].

Sincerity is the characteristic that demonstrates the performance of the services to the consumer. Excitement is a dimension related to the novelty of the event. The sophisticated dimension is related to the resort's exceptional experience. The competence component is concerned with service performance. Ruggedness is a quality that connects to the natural experience [16].

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The initial step is to collect data from internet reviews, which will be analyzed with the help of the Provalis program. The data obtained was sampled between 2008 and 2020, during the time of observation. The online reviews are user-generated material, and they are a subset of the data collection that will be processed further [15][16][17]. Following the data extraction procedure, the data is cleaned and the legitimate data is selected for further processing. Following the procedure, an exploratory factor analysis based on the brand personality dictionary was carried out. In summary, the method will examine the specific phrases within the context of the evaluations that are connected to each component of brand personality.

Table 1. Research Method

Research Methodology	Exploratory study
Type of sampling	Nonstatistical sampling
Sample	2008 - 2020 dataset
Data collection methods	Extraction from user-generated content
Information sources	TripAdvisor online platform
Key contributors	Resort online reviews
Data analysis methods	Brand Personality exploratory factor analysis with Brand Personality Dictionary [18]
Study period	2008 - 2020
Source	Based on [18, 19]

IV. RESULTS

4.1 Brand Personality exploratory factor analysis

The summary demonstrates that the Resort gained a dominant Sincerity dimension in the Resort data from 2008 to 2020. (Table 4). The second most popular review category is sophistication, while the third most popular review category is enthusiasm. This dimension is concerned with cheerfulness as something new, energetic, and bright.

Table 4. Brand Personality Dimension Frequency

No	Dimension	Dimension Frequency
1	SINCERITY	385
2	SOPHISTICATION	145
3	EXCITEMENT	120
4	RUGGEDNESS	48
5	COMPETENCE	38

Sincerity

This dimension is a dimension that is generally conveyed by keywords in reviews in the dataset (Table 5). For example, case (2) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) conveys that the resort staff is accommodating and "friendly". In addition, case (6) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) conveyed that the room is clean, the bed is comfortable, and the pool has a good size "good" with a view overlooking the rice fields.

In addition, there is also a case (26) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) that conveys that all the staff is friendly and "welcoming" them when it comes to this resort. Many reviews fall into this category featuring a performance from staff appreciated by resort guests. Another example is the case from (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), who said that he was warmly greeted "warmly" by the staff upon arrival at the resort.

Another example of a case is the case of (50) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), who said that the staff is good with the keyword "kind". In some cases, the above are reviews that have positive sentiments. This dimension keyword is closely related to the adjectives of resort staff obtained from the experience of the resort visitors when interacting with their staff.

In addition, there is also an example of a case (52) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), who said that the experience of staying at the resort is pleasant, with the keyword "pleasant". Furthermore, the case of (54) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021) said that the staff of the resort is amicable and helpful, with the keyword "helpful".

Furthermore, the case of (88) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) said that the staff in this place quickly responded with the keyword "responsive" in addressing various problems/complaints from visitors to the resort.

Sincerity dimension means a brand that is seen as a humble, honest, trustworthy, and also cheerful person. In addition, brands that provide sincere service have a commitment to consumers or attention to the needs of consumers.

Table 5. Sincerity Dimension Keyword in Context

Case number	Pre-Keyword Context	Keyword	Post-Keyword Context
2	We stayed 2 days on this resort was really wonderful, the service from their staff really helpful and	friendly	. The view is also amazing from our room. I really love the flowers bath up decorations so romantic. Will be back on this resort again next time. Thank you

Sophistication

An example of this dimension can be conveyed from the case of (1) (TripAdvisor, Mar 2021), who told me that he had a "beautiful" experience while staying at the resort. Furthermore, the service was also outstanding, "excellent" with spotless rooms and very kind staff, as stated in the case of (04) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021).

Another example is conveyed by the case (20) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), which tells that the resort is a perfect and luxurious "luxurious" room, with a good view of the pool. In the reviews mentioned, indeed, the resort received reviews that placed it at the top of the perception of visitors who wrote reviews on TripAdvisor.

Furthermore, in the case of (14) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), (42) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), and (84) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) also delivered reviews using the word "beautiful" or beautiful for the atmosphere of the resort environment and swimming pool at the resort. Another example is the case of (22) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), who said that apart from the friendly staff, the view at the resort was also "spectacular".

Furthermore, in the case of (52) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), who conveyed that the experience of staying at the resort was enjoyable and the view was magnificent with the keyword "gorgeous". In addition, he gave a 10/10 review rating and said he would be back soon to visit the resort.

Another review was submitted by the case of (343) (TripAdvisor, Oct 2020), who said that the rooms at the resort are gorgeous with a touch of high-end décor, with the keyword "high class". Furthermore, in the case of (351) (TripAdvisor, Oct 2020), which conveys the resort is the perfect place for honeymooners and the pool area of the restaurant is very "pretty".

Excitement

An example of this dimension can be reviewed from the case (8) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), which conveys that the room is very modern, with the keyword "modern", and this makes her enthusiastic. Furthermore, the case (16) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) also conveyed that the villa is impressive "awesome", and furniture, Netflix channels, and save everything provided. They will also come back again to this place as they have good service.

In addition, there is also a case that conveys the case (22) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) that modern furniture and design "modern", with a quiet environment. Still related to furniture, the case (50) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) conveyed that the furniture looks new, "new" and good. He had a pleasant experience staying at Kamala and will be returning to the resort for a vacation.

Another example is conveyed by the case of (38) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), who said that the resort is the best choice during the Covid-19 pandemic virus because visitors can feel safe and live a fresh air "fresh" so this place is worth visiting. A fresh keyword is a word that has a positive sentiment and makes the spirit, novelty, freshness of the resort.

This excitement dimension consists of keywords that give spirit and enthusiasm so that visitors are excited to stay at the resort and get an unforgettable experience. Modern artistic rooms and new furniture become a frequent reviewed facility, especially for this dimension of excitement.

Ruggedness

This dimension elaborated from the case review (10) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021) which conveys that the room has a great view of the jungle. The same was also conveyed by the case (12) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), which conveyed that when she swam, she saw a lovely view overlooking the forest "jungle".

In the case (172), (TripAdvisor, Dec 2020) conveyed that the infinity swimming pool very beautiful when the sun goes down "sunset". This scene is part of a dimension that talks about more outdoor-oriented personalities such as forests, sunsets, nature.

There is also a negative sentiment in this dimension, namely from the case (521) (TripAdvisor, Mar 2020), which conveys a bit less comfortable. Because it feels that in the environment of this resort there are developments in some areas that make them less comfortable "uncomfortable". However, overall, they conveyed satisfaction with the service and facilities and will return to the resort.

The dimensions of Ruggedness relate to the strength, durability, capability of the brand in meeting the needs of consumers. This dimension is generally present in brands or products for men, outdoor activities displaying more solid or dark color visualizations, and displaying a sturdy font.

Competence

An example of this dimension is the case of (80) (TripAdvisor, Feb 2021), saying that the price is good value, the staff is friendly, and the villa is extraordinarily "glorious". In addition, there is a case (194) (TripAdvisor, Dec 2020) which conveyed that this resort is a place that is guaranteed suitable "guaranteed" and visitors will get a different experience than other places.

In addition, there is also a case (228) (TripAdvisor, Dec 2020), who conveys that the facilities at the resort are "complete", so she recommends others to stay here. Another example of this dimension is the case (275) (TripAdvisor, Nov 2020), which conveys that the food is good and tastes good with a great view "outstanding". In addition, there is also a case (307) (TripAdvisor, Nov 2020), which conveys that the main pool is impressive "outstanding" and they will come back to this resort for a vacation.

In addition to reviews with positive sentiment, there are also reviews with negative sentiments, such as those delivered by the case (343) (TripAdvisor, Oct 2020). The place has calm and clean sanitation, but they experience "experienced" fewer good things because the water does not flow well, the water heater should also not be bad, so it takes a long time to fill the water in stages. However, overall, they are still satisfied, and from this experience, they want to come back again for a vacation.

Next is the case of (194) (TripAdvisor, Dec 2020), who conveyed that the resort is very comfortable and pleasant and "guaranteed" with extraordinary service. Furthermore, in the case of (228) (TripAdvisor, Dec 2020) and (242) (TripAdvisor, Dec 2020) mentioned a review using the word "complete" or complete for the existing facilities at the resort.

Another example was presented by the case of (323) (TripAdvisor, Nov 2020), who told if she felt safe "safe" staying at the resort during the Covid-19 virus pandemic because this place already follows health protocols for the prevention of the Covid-19 virus. Next up is the case of (527) (TripAdvisor, Mar 2020), which conveys that the resort has clean rooms, well-organized and safe, with the keyword "secure". This dimension of competence relates to the ability of the brand to meet the needs of customer service responsibly, quality and reliable brand, products that have high intelligence capabilities.

V. CONCLUSION

According to the findings of this study, the resort is certainly strong in two personalities: Sincerity and Sophistication. It is an example of a Provalis software program study for classifying Aaker brand personality, 1997 for unstructured datasets that are TripAdvisor evaluations for the resort.

Sincerity implies that the brand is perceived to be a person who is humble, honest, trustworthy, and joyful. Brands that provide genuine service commit to or pay attention to the requirements of their customers. While Sophistication refers to consumers' perception of the brand as a person of class, high status, or glamour. This luxury emanates from the brand's identity, which has sophisticated aspects. This prestige radiates to customers, which is essential in the context of a resort since the resort is linked with a location that is more than just a house/villa but a luxurious, sophisticated, glittering environment.

The initial stage of the analytic method is tabulating the frequency of words, followed by tabulating the frequency of phrases, and lastly classification based on the brand personality keywords. The unifying thread is that each brand's word frequency tabulation and phrase and keyword frequency tabulation produce relevant and convergent findings.

However, the process of weighing the dominating dimensions and groupings in a dataset necessitates a far more quantitative methodology. We may set dimension dimensions with benefits and dimensions that need to be maintained or enhanced using a quantitative method. This research's subsequent procedure must also be evaluated on a yearly basis to reflect the resort's performance.

The process of weighting the dominant dimensions and groups in a dataset, on the other hand, needs a considerably more quantitative technique. We can use a quantitative technique to define dimension dimensions with advantages and dimensions that need to be maintained or improved. The succeeding method of this study must also be assessed on a yearly basis to represent the resort's performance.

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